

PLEIADES

NEWSLETTER
02 | 2025

PLEIADES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101192721.

**Funded by
the European Union**

PUBLICATIONS

TWO TECHNICAL BROCHURES PUBLISHED

Two technical brochures were published in fall 2025.

The first brochure, released in October, introduces the development of passive PIC based multi-sensors – one core activity within the PLEIADES project.

It highlights how these sensors can transform aerospace composites manufacturing and contribute directly to the future of aerospace.

The second brochure, published in November, deals with the topic of induction welding, explaining why welding is an important alternative to conventional joining methods and how this technology can make aircraft lighter, more efficient and easier to maintain.

[READ AND DOWNLOAD THE BROCHURES HERE](#)

ARTICLE ABOUT HIGH-TEMPERATURE VITRIMERS PUBLISHED IN "POLYMER"

Festus Ifeanyi Anagwu, Daniel Preston and Alex Skordos from PLEIADES partner Cranfield University published an article in POLYMER (Volume 342, 1 January 2026): "Cure kinetics, glass transition and chemoviscosity models for an aerospace-grade disulphide-based benzoxazine vitrimer".

The paper highlights an important difference in the rheological behaviour of vitrimers compared to conventional thermosets. Due to bond exchange during the cure, these materials show a plateau in viscosity in the region a conventional

thermoset exhibits very high viscosity as a result of gelation. Effectively the steep increase in viscosity at gelation is suppressed.

[READ THE ARTICLE HERE](#)

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

Deliverable 12.4. is out, presenting the projects basics, objectives and project partners in form of a video. It is available

on YouTube and for download in the repository on the PLEIADES website.

[WATCH THE VIDEO ON YOUTUBE](#)

PLEIADES IS ON ZENODO NOW

We're officially on Zenodo, making our research outputs openly accessible to everyone.

You can now find and cite our datasets, publications, and other materials directly through our Zenodo community.

Let's keep advancing open science and data sharing together!

[ZENODO](#)

USERNAME: PLEIADES_SUSTAINABILITY
FULL NAME: PLEIADES

EVENTS

HALF-YEARLY PLEIADES PROJECT MEETING IN ATHENS

On November 3–4, 2025, the PLEIADES consortium gathered in Athens for our bi-annual project meeting. Host was PLEIADES partner NTUA - The National Technical University of Athens. Over two productive days, partners discussed the current project progress, reviewed

upcoming tasks, and shared updates from each Work Package.

Our experts from across Europe exchanged insights on materials, induction welding, sensing technologies, and digital integration — all key pillars driving the PLEIADES vision forward.

SALIENT PROJECT CROSS FERTILISATION WORKSHOP

On 11 June 2025, PLEIADES participated in a cross-fertilisation workshop from the SALIENT Project.

The event took place online and brought together 16 Horizon Europe projects, aiming to align innovation and to identify

shared challenges, solutions and future funding needs.

Discover the main drivers behind the projects and which key technologies could be identified!

[READ THE SUMMARY HERE](#)

PLEIADES MEETS JEC FORUM DACH

Project partner EuCIA was in Dresden at the JEC Forum DACH 2025, which took place on October 21st - 22nd.

Organised by JEC in partnership with AVK, the event promotes innovation, business development, and cross-border collaboration across the composites sector. It was the ideal opportunity to provide information about PLEIADES and its goal to develop sustainable aircraft for the future and advance composite aerostructures.

PLEIADES PROJECT PRESENTED AT ADVANCED ENGINEERING EVENT

Chris Worrall from TWI (PLEIADES Project Leader) presented details of the PLEIADES project at the Advanced Engineering show at the NEC in Birmingham, UK.

Advanced Engineering, which took place on 29-30 October 2025, brings together the brightest minds in design, engineering, and manufacturing to solve real-world challenges, accelerate innovation, develop skills, and build a more sustainable future.

Uniting all industrial ecosystems to help drive high-value manufacturing and supply chain solutions, the event included dedicated zones for industries including aerospace, automotive, defence, and composites, as well as features and

demos, and a suite of expert talks from leading names drawn from industry – including a number of TWI Industrial Member companies.

Chris Worrall joined the experts presenting during the show, using his knowledge and expertise to speak on the PLEIADES project.

His talk, 'PLEIADES: Integrated Sensor-Based Robotic Induction Welding,' took place during a session on 'Invisible Intelligence' as part of the conference's Composites Engineering Forum.

[VIEW THE CONFERENCE PRESENTATION HERE](#)

PLEIADES PRESENTATION AT 15TH EASN CONFERENCE IN MADRID

On October 14th-17th, the 15th EASN International Conference took place in Madrid, Spain at the Universidad Politecnica de Madrid (UPM). The event was dedicated to "Innovation in Aviation & Space towards sustainability today and tomorrow".

The EASN Conference Series is a platform for fostering dialogue and collaboration among key stakeholders in aviation and space, including representatives from academia, industry, research organizations, and policymaking bodies. Through plenary talks, thematic sessions, and interactive discussions, participants can

explore groundbreaking advancements and innovative approaches to address today's and tomorrow's sustainability challenges.

On day 2 of the conference, Harry Zervos from PLEIADES Partner ICCS (Institute of Communications and Computer Systems) of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) spoke about the PLEIADES project in his presentation "Photonics-Integrated Induction Welding for Digital, Sustainable Manufacturing & MRO".

LEARN MORE ABOUT THE [EASN CONFERENCE](#)

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